

Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of 2,3,15,16-tetramethyl/ethyl/*p*-tolyl-1,4,14,17-tetraazacyclohexacosyl,3,14,16-tetraene

R. N. Prasad*, Seema Gupta and Sarita Jangir

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : rnp_1949@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : Hexacoordinated tetraazamacrocyclic complexes of the general formula [MLX₂] (where L = N₄ macrocycle having 26-membered ring, X = Cl or NCS and M = Mg, Ca, Sr or Ba) have been synthesized by 2+2 cyclocondensation reactions of 1,9-diaminononane with α -diketones viz. 2,3-butanedione, 3,4-hexanedione or 4,4'-dimethylbenzil in the presence of metal ions as templates. The synthesized complexes were characterized by elemental analyses, conductance measurements and IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes, alkaline earth metal complexes, conductances, IR spectra, NMR spectra.

Introduction

Interest in the studies of macrocyclic complexes has developed during the recent years due to their close resemblance with the biomolecules and they have been used in the identification of diseases and normal tissues¹. Fe^{III} complexes of a tetraazamacrocyclic, 1,4,7,10-tetrakis(carboxymethyl)-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane are potential contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)². For the synthesis of such systems transition metal ions have generally been used as templates³, however, a few syntheses have involved alkaline earth metal templates also. Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of 18-membered azamacrocyclic have been synthesized by (2+2) cyclocondensation of 2,6-diformylpyridine with *o*-phenylenediamine⁴. Synthesis of a 24-membered azamacrocyclic has been achieved by cyclocondensation of 2,6-diacetylpyridine and *N,N*-bis(2-aminoethyl)-2-methoxyethylamine using Ba²⁺ as a template⁵. Alkaline earth metal complexes of 18-membered tetraazamacrocyclics derived from (2+2) cyclocondensation of α -diketones and 1,5-diaminopentane have been reported earlier from our laboratories⁶ and in the present paper such complexes of 26-membered tetraazamacrocyclics derived from 1,9-diaminononane and α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 3,4-hexanedione and 4,4'-dimethylbenzil are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of metal chlorides or nitrates with 1,9-diaminononane and α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione,

3,4-hexanedione or 4,4'-dimethylbenzil in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratios (in the presence of NCS⁻ ions in case of Ca, Sr and Ba) have resulted in the formation of M^{II} complexes (1) of 26-membered tetraazamacrocyclics 2,3,15,16-tetramethyl/ethyl/*p*-tolyl-1,4,14,17-tetraazacyclohexacosyl,3,14,16-tetraene according to Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of alkaline earth metal complexes of tetraazamacrocyclics.

The resulting macrocyclic complexes have 12-membered chelate rings which are not improbable due to the flexibility of the ring and have been reported earlier in

case of the complexes of long chain flexible bidentate ligands such as Co^{III} complexes of diaminoalkanes H₂N(CH₂)_nNH₂ (n = 2–14)⁷ and platinum and palladium complexes of diphosphines Bu^t₂P(CH₂)_nPBu^t₂ (n = 9, 10 or 12)⁸. Moreover such a chelate ring would be more stable in metal complexes of macrocyclic ligands since macrocyclic complexes are often stabilized to a greater extent by the macrocyclic effect "multiple juxtapositional fixedness"⁹.

These complexes are isolated as yellow, brown or white solids which decompose on heating. They are insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, ether, nitromethane and *n*-hexane but soluble in DMSO. Their analyses and characteristics are given in Table 1. Molar conductances of the complexes (Table 1) are generally low, supporting their non-electrolytic behaviour. Thus the chloro or thiocyanato groups are coordinated to the metal atom supporting hexa-coordinated geometry around the metal atom. However, the higher values in some cases may be due to the replacement of weakly coordinated chloro or thiocyanato groups by solvent molecules.

Infrared spectra :

All the complexes exhibit a strong band at 1600 cm⁻¹

which is assigned to the coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and no absorption band at 1700 or 3200–3300 cm⁻¹ due to unreacted C=O or NH₂ groups. Thus the C=O groups of α -diketones and NH₂ groups of the diamine have condensed to give C=N linkage. Similar observations have been made by other workers in case of metal complexes of other macrocycles¹⁰. A broad band at ~550 cm⁻¹ is assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$. In case of thiocyanato complexes of Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II}, bands at 2050–2070 cm⁻¹ are attributed to *N*-bonded thiocyanato group. Lowering of this frequency as compared to that reported for free thiocyanate (2100 cm⁻¹) supports the coordination of thiocyanate to the metal atom¹¹.

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectra :

¹H NMR spectra of the complexes have been recorded and the δ values (ppm) for different protons are given in Table 2. In free 1,9-diaminononane, the α -CH₂ protons appear as a triplet at δ 2.68 ppm, while β and other CH₂ protons appear as a quintet at δ 1.31 ppm. In KIM (2) the α -CH₂ protons have been reported to appear as a triplet at δ 3.64 ppm and β -CH₂ protons as a quintet at δ 2.11 ppm¹². This downfield shift as compared to the protons of free diamine is due to deshielding by π -electrons of

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of M^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles

Complex	Colour and temp. of decomp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analyses (%) : Found (Calcd.)			Molar cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
			M	N	Cl	
[(Me ₄ [26]tetraeneN ₄)MgCl ₂]	Brown (160)	26	4.71 (4.74)	10.86 (10.94)	13.66 (13.85)	18
[(Et ₄ [26]tetraeneN ₄)MgCl ₂]	White (170)	45	4.27 (4.27)	9.87 (9.86)	12.67 (12.48)	76
[((4-MePh) ₄ [26]tetraeneN ₄)MgCl ₂]	White (190)	47	3.03 (2.96)	6.79 (6.82)	8.53 (8.64)	82
[(Me ₄ [26]tetraeneN ₄)Ca(NCS) ₂]	Brown (203)	48	6.97 (6.99)	9.71 (9.77)	-	32
[(Et ₄ [26]tetraeneN ₄)Ca(NCS) ₂]	Light yellow (215)	30	6.32 (6.37)	8.91 (8.90)	-	186
[(Me ₄ [26]tetraeneN ₄)Sr(NCS) ₂]	Brown (205)	51	14.10 (14.12)	9.01 (9.02)	-	14
[(E ₄ [26]tetraeneN ₄)Sr(NCS) ₂]	Light yellow (200)	33	12.89 (12.95)	8.23 (8.28)	-	25
[(Me ₄ [26]tetraeneN ₄)Ba(NCS) ₂]	Brown (170)	31	20.42 (20.49)	8.34 (8.35)	-	9
[(Et ₄ [26]tetraeneN ₄)Ba(NCS) ₂]	Light brown (195)	30	18.84 (18.89)	7.72 (7.71)	-	27

Table 2. ^1H NMR chemical shifts (δ , ppm) of tetraazamacrocyclic complexes

Complex	Amine residue		Ketone residue		Aromatic protons
	$\alpha\text{-CH}_2$	$\beta\text{-CH}_2$	CH_3^a	CH_2^b	
$[(\text{Me}_4[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{MgCl}_2]$	2.77b	1.27b	0.84t	-	-
$[(\text{Et}_4[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{MgCl}_2]$	2.71t	1.27b	0.81t	2.23m	-
$[\{(4\text{-MePh})_4[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4\}\text{MgCl}_2]$	2.74t	1.27b	2.41d	-	7.26d, 7.35d ^a , 7.50d ^a , 7.70d
$[(\text{Me}_4[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Ca}(\text{NCS})_2]$	2.77b	1.27b	0.84t	-	-
$[(\text{Et}_4[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Ca}(\text{NCS})_2]$	2.72t	1.28b	0.82t	2.24m	-
$[(\text{Me}_4[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Sr}(\text{NCS})_2]$	2.77b	1.27b	0.84t	-	-
$[(\text{Et}_4[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Sr}(\text{NCS})_2]$	2.73t	1.28b	0.81t	2.22m	-
$[(\text{Me}_4[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Ba}(\text{NCS})_2]$	2.77b	1.27b	0.84t	-	-
$[(\text{Et}_4[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Ba}(\text{NCS})_2]$	2.72t	1.27b	0.82t	2.23m	-

^aMerge together and appear as a sort of triplet.
s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, m = multiplet, b = broad.

C=N bond. The free macrocycles, though not isolated, would have exhibited these resonances at almost similar positions as in KIM. In the macrocyclic complexes, $\alpha\text{-CH}_2$ protons exhibit a triplet at δ 2.71–2.77 ppm (J 6–7 Hz) and β and other methylene protons exhibit a broad peak at δ 1.27–1.28 ppm. Upfield shift of α - and $\beta\text{-CH}_2$ protons in these complexes as compared to KIM supports the coordination of nitrogen to metal atom in the macrocyclic complexes.

Methyl and methylene protons of the ketone residue of macrocyclic complexes exhibit very weak signals. In the complexes (1, $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$) of the macrocycle derived from 2,3-butanedione ($\text{CH}_3\text{COCOCH}_3$) and diamine the methyl protons of the ketone residue appear as a triplet at δ 0.84 ppm due to the long range coupling with $\alpha\text{-CH}_2$ protons of the amine residue, similar to the homoallylic type coupling observed in the compounds having unsaturated linkage of the type $\text{H}_3\text{CC}=\text{NCH}_2$ ¹³. In free 2,3-

butanedione, the methyl protons appear at δ 1.46 ppm. Upfield shifting of methyl protons in the macrocyclic complexes confirms the coordination of nitrogen of the macrocycle to the metal atoms. In free 3,4-hexanedione ($\text{CH}_3^a\text{CH}_2^b\text{COCOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), the methyl protons appear as a triplet at δ 1.10 ppm and the methylene protons as a quartet at δ 2.77 ppm. In the complexes (1, $\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$) the methyl protons (CH_3^a) of ketone residue are shifted very slightly to high field (δ 0.81–0.82 ppm) and this may be due to the fact that these protons are away from the C=N group and hence are not affected much by coordination. The methylene protons (CH_2^b) of the ketone residue appear as a multiplet at δ 2.22–2.24 ppm. High field shifting of these CH_2 peaks supports the coordination of C=N group of the macrocycle to the metal atom. In Mg^{II} complex (1, $\text{R} = p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$) of the macrocycle derived from 4,4'-dimethylbenzil, the CH_3 protons give a doublet at δ 2.41 ppm. This may be due to the long range coupling of CH_3 protons with CH protons of the ring. In the aromatic region, four doublets at δ 7.26, 7.35, 7.50 and 7.70 ppm are observed and this may be due to the non-equivalence of aromatic protons as a result of restricted rotation. Because of being in the close proximity two of these doublets merge together and appear as a sort of triplet.

Experimental

Materials :

2,3-Butanedione (Fluka), 3,4-hexanedione (Aldrich),

4,4'-dimethylbenzil (Aldrich) and 1,9-diaminononane (Aldrich) were used as supplied. MgCl₂·6H₂O (B.D.H.), Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (B.D.H.), SrCl₂·6H₂O (E. Merck) and BaCl₂·2H₂O (Glaxo) were of A.R. grade. Methanol, ethanol and butanol were distilled before use.

Analytical methods and physical measurements :

Magnesium, calcium and strontium were determined volumetrically using EDTA, barium gravimetrically as barium sulphate, nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method and chloride gravimetrically as AgCl. IR spectra were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer as KBr pellets in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ on a Zeol FX 90Q FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as reference. Conductances were measured in DMSO using a Systronics Direct Reading Conductivity Meter-304.

Synthesis of Mg^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles :

MgCl₂·6H₂O (2.8 mmol) was dissolved in 20 ml butanol and a butanolic solution of 2,3-butanedione (5.6 mmol in 10 ml) was added to it. Then a butanolic solution of 1,9-diaminononane (5.6 mmol in 10 ml) was added with continuous stirring. The contents were stirred for ~6 h and the solid product obtained was filtered, washed with butanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reactions of MgCl₂·6H₂O were carried out with 1,9-diaminononane and 3,4-hexanedione or 4,4'-dimethylbenzil to afford Mg^{II} complexes of 26-membered tetraazamacrocycles.

Synthesis of Ca^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles :

To the butanolic solution of Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (1.7 mmol in ~20 ml), a butanolic solution of 2,3-butanedione (3.4 mmol in 10 ml) was added. To this reaction mixture, butanolic solution of 1,9-diaminononane (3.4 mmol in 10 ml) was added with continuous stirring. As no solid appeared, a butanolic solution of potassium thiocyanate (3.4 mmol) was added. Stirring was continued for ~6 h and the temperature was maintained at 60 °C throughout the course of the reaction. The solid product obtained was filtered, washed with butanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reaction of Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O was carried out with 1,9-diaminononane and 3,4-hexanedione to afford corresponding Ca^{II} complex of 26-membered tetraazamacrocycle.

Synthesis of Sr^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles :

To the methanolic solution of SrCl₂·6H₂O (1.7 mmol

in ~20 ml), a methanolic solution of 2,3-butanedione (3.4 mmol in 10 ml) was added. To this, 1,9-diaminononane (3.4 mmol in 10 ml methanol) was added drop by drop with constant stirring. As no solid appeared, a methanolic solution of potassium thiocyanate (3.4 mmol) was added with continuous stirring. Stirring was continued for ~10 h. The solid product obtained was filtered, washed with methanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reaction of SrCl₂·6H₂O was carried out with 1,9-diaminononane and 3,4-hexanedione and Sr^{II} complex of corresponding 26-membered tetraazamacrocycle was isolated.

Synthesis of Ba^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles :

BaCl₂·2H₂O (2.1 mmol) was dissolved in ethanol-water (1 : 1, 20 ml) and an ethanolic solution of 2,3-butanedione (4.2 mmol in 10 ml) was added. Then ethanolic solution of 1,9-diaminononane (4.2 mmol in 10 ml) was added drop by drop with constant stirring. As no solid appeared, ethanolic solution of potassium thiocyanate (4.2 mmol) was added. Stirring was continued for ~10 h and solid product obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reaction of BaCl₂·2H₂O with 1,9-diaminononane and 3,4-hexanedione was carried out and Ba^{II} complex of the corresponding 26-membered tetraazamacrocycle was isolated.

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